

Blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity for Routing in Inter-Domain Networks

Engin Zeydan, *Senior Member, IEEE*, Josep Mangués, Suayb S. Arslan, *Senior Member, IEEE* and Yekta Turk

Abstract—Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) has emerged lately as an identity and access management framework typically implemented based on Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) and allows device owners to administer and control their own data. In this paper, a blockchain (BCN)-based SSI system has been developed as a new identity plane to enable routing device owners in Autonomous Systems (ASs) to have greater control over inter-domain networks (IDNs), potentially across multiple paths that comply with routing device-defined preferences. The proposed system provides identity management, authentication and transparent information about routers, attested by ASs, while maintaining the privacy of sensitive network details. Device-level information and preferences are protected by BCN-based SSI. We used a GNS3 network emulation test bed and Hyperledger Indy distributed identity management system to test the proposed solution’s AS convergence time and credential operation time respectively. Experiment results demonstrated that when the proposed routing system was used in combination with the BCN-based SSI credential management platform, the convergence time for the Inter-AS and Intra-AS systems became longer as the number of routers increased, whereas the credential operations had shorter processing times.

Index Terms—self-sovereign, digital identity, blockchain, routing, autonomous system.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE current state of the Internet does not give Autonomous System (AS) sufficient visibility and authority over on-path forwarding devices in Inter-Domain Networks (IDNs). This means that there is limited information about the configurations of the network devices, which leads to a lack of trust in the forwarding paths. In addition, applications that require certain router features cannot reach their full potential, and the lack of ability to influence traffic routing results in communications using undesirable or unsafe routes while potentially desirable paths remain unused. While this works for many applications (such as public Internet or non-critical services), it can lead to performance, compliance, and security issues if the chosen path does not match the network properties required by end users or Cloud Service Providers (CSPs). However, in some cases, there are various applications

that require certain network properties when routing traffic. For example, some applications (such as financial transactions, healthcare information, legal and compliance data or government communications) require that sensitive data never leave a particular jurisdiction, which means that traffic can only be routed through authenticated routers that operate in specific countries or regions. Governments and critical infrastructure operators may also have preferences, such as avoiding the involvement of unauthenticated network devices in routing decisions to avoid potential security risks [1]. In such cases, traffic in IDNs must be routed only over paths consisting of specific, trusted devices. Solutions such as Trusted Path Routing [2] can enforce that sensitive traffic is routed only through trusted devices.

Within an AS, routers are distinguished by their unique IP addresses, which allow them to establish communication and exchange routing information with other routers. In today’s Internet landscape, encryption techniques have become prevalent to maintain the confidentiality of data during communication. However, even with encryption, if Internet Protocol (IP) addresses of routers or routing protocols (such as Border Gateway Protocol (BGP), OSPF (Open Shortest Path First), or IS-IS (Intermediate System to Intermediate System)) used to exchange routing information with other routers are compromised by observing metadata attributes, the routing information could potentially be hijacked and traffic could be redirected to unauthorized destinations, resulting in potential security and data breaches [3]. In addition, the secure distribution and safeguarding of keys can be a major challenge due to the susceptibility of encryption methods to vulnerabilities such as quantum computer attacks and weaknesses in ciphering methods. Routers can also use various authentication mechanisms, such as passwords or digital certificates, to verify the identity of other routers before exchanging routing information. If these authentication mechanisms are also compromised, an attacker may be able to gain unauthorized access to the routing information and redirect traffic to unauthorized destinations.

To overcome these challenges, an alternative approach can be taken that does not rely on encryption alone, but uses Blockchain Network (BCN)-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) (e.g. the authors in [4] propose different architectural approaches for using BCN-based SSI in vehicular networks). This technique can ensure confidentiality, integrity, availability, and reliability of routing information within self-managed systems by routing data over trusted network devices and links. This method ensures the validity of routers through strict authentication mechanisms, guarantees that data communica-

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Fig. 1: Uncontrolled Inter-AS routing problem.

tions remain private, and complements encryption techniques to strengthen overall data protection, even in the case of eavesdropping and interception of data or metadata. The next subsection contains an example that illustrates the need for secure routing in IDNs.

A. An Example for Necessity of Secure Routing in IDNs

A potential problem with inter-domain routing in a network of different ASs is illustrated in this section. As shown in Fig. 1, assume that there is already a connection between AS-2 and AS-3 via border routers. AS-3 can access various Internet and cloud services through AS-2. Consider the situation where a new connection is established with a new connection AS-1 and a border router AS-3. After this new connection, IP addresses announced by AS-2 may be inadvertently announced by AS-1. In this case, since AS-3 trusts these routes, it performs injections by announcing these IP addresses to other internal routers within AS-3. In this case, access to all Internet and cloud services accessed by AS-3 via AS-2 is interrupted. This is a typical scenario where BGP hijacking can occur [5]. Such issues (including a cyber attack on services provided by CSPs) can occur after a misconfiguration [6] and still continues to be a risk. In next subsection, we introduce the concept of distributed management for digital identities in the context of decentralized networks.

B. Distributed Management for Digital Identities

The emergence of Web 3.0 has boosted new diverse, decentralized applications with advanced security features [7]. However, there are still several challenges that need to be addressed to guarantee security and trust in decentralized networks. For example, for security, Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) is used in centralized identity management systems which is expensive and centralized. Moreover, services can be disrupted in case Centralized Authority (CA) makes an error (which can be catastrophic for mission-critical vehicle services). For this reason, Distributed Identity Management (DIM) solutions

such as Hyperledger Indy¹ have been proposed to build trust without relying on PKI. By relying on selective disclosure and Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs), only limited required data elements are provided as proof in DIM solutions. For example, proof that an AS and its internal routers are eligible to participate into routing in IDNs can be validated without providing additional information such as issuer data.

DIM is still a key open issue [8] and a solution based on Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs) can be very powerful if some of the key issues (e.g., power, network stability, some form of security attack, etc.) can be properly addressed. There are several recent works aimed at providing blockchain-based solutions for different aspects of identity and access management. Tong *et al* [9] addresses domain interoperability and compatibility issues in multidomain Internet of Things (IoT) systems by utilizing a consortium blockchain and tailored authentication protocols. Also, Huang *et al* [10] presents a unified blockchain-based framework for secure cross-domain authorization and authentication in smart cities, emphasizing techniques such as privacy-preserving encryption and user revocation mechanisms. However, these studies might be limited in their ability to address the aforementioned issues with regards to routing in IDNs.

A BCN-based SSI in a routing in IDNs architecture can help overcome some of these limitations. The paper in [4] presents various options to consider for BCN-based SSI architectures. BCN-based mechanisms such as reputation systems and proof-of-work can help build trust between routing in IDNs devices. There exist many approaches utilizing routing in IDNs, BCNs, smart contracts, Interplanetary File System (IPFS), SSI ledger, and a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) communication channel for secure, private and efficient data sharing, trust establishment and authentication purposes [11]. In particular, routing in IDNs has been used with BCNs to provide trust and privacy in several previous works, e.g., in [12], authors proposed the BCN to store the routing prefixes from different group of autonomous systems in a hierarchical structure. However, classical routing in IDNs can suffer from various attacks including adversarial attacks, authentication, and model inversion attacks which need to be enhanced [13], even if Machine Learning (ML) techniques are used [3]. The authors in [14] propose a blockchain-based approach, called Cochain-SC, which combines two levels of mitigation, intra-domain and inter-domain DDoS mitigation. The authors in [15] propose the decentralized blockchain-based route registration framework to protect the origin of IP address prefix. The next subsection defines our contributions, which propose a new architecture that uses BCN-based SSI for identity management in IDNs and enables authentication and integrity of router data while preserving privacy.

C. Proposed BCN-based SSI Solution in IDNs

All of the above approaches provide different routing in IDNs management techniques, either as a standalone solution (such as using statistical analysis for adversarial attacks or ML

¹Online: <https://www.hyperledger.org/use/hyperledger-indy>, Available: January 2023.

Fig. 2: The integration of DID into a blockchain network.

for anomaly detection) or in conjunction with storing routing information in BCN. BCN have been used in some studies to retain routing information [15], [12], but previous studies have not evaluated the flexibility that would be gained with network devices that actually have a digital identity. Hence, there is a lack of a platform that can simultaneously provide integrity, reliability and authentication while keeping routing whole device data private. Therefore, in this paper, we propose a new architectural and design approach that uses BCN-based SSI for routing in IDNs so that authentication, reliability and integrity of the router data, as well as control of routing information diffusion over IDNs with the identity of network devices is achieved. By using the issuer mechanisms of SSI BCN, restrictions can be placed on device identities, such as disclosure of uncontrolled, invalid or conflicting routing information. Moreover, the BCN-based SSI can be used for both configuration and inventory management of network devices.

The BCN-based SSI framework for routing in IDNs enables ASs and router owners to control their identities and manage access to their resources without relying on a central authority. It leverages the principles of SSI, which allow device owners to create and manage their own identities and control access to their data. In this system, each owner of ASs and routers has a unique identifier stored on an BCN. When a routing request is initiated from one AS to another, the border routers use their SSIs to authenticate themselves and prove that they have the necessary permissions to connect to the requested resources. The BCN is used to verify the identity of border routers and authorize the routing request. By using BCN technology, a decentralized and trusted solution can be provided to ensure the security and privacy of routing requests in the IDNs. In this paper, we prepared a test setup using routers and a BCN-based SSI in the Graphical Network Simulator-3 (GNS3) emulation and Hyperledger Indy environment for validation purposes. The experimental results show that the implemented system has a shorter duration for credential operations, while routing

in the IDNs system takes more time as the number of border and internal routers increases.

II. DESIGN ASPECTS AND USE CASE

A. Digital Identity based Routing

A promising approach to ensure trust in data exchange between entities (e.g., source and destination AS) is to use DLTs like BCN to manage router information. When router updates are stored in a BCN ledger, the risk of information misuse is minimized. For example, in IDN routing, each AS has its own routing policies and protocols and interact with each other via BGP. Authentication mechanisms such as digital signatures and certificates can be used to verify the authenticity of information exchanged between ASs, but routing decisions are made locally by each AS based on its own policies and metrics. On the other hand, setting up a single centralized routing agent in IDNs can lead to malfunction and scalability issues in dynamic environments.

Information stored in DLT can provide proof of trust when routing and data exchanges in IDNs, and thus has the potential to minimize the risk of information misuse. Note that the data stored in the ledger is limited to the information explicitly requested. On the other hand, all private data exchanged between entities can still be kept secure. Integration of routing in IDNs with DLT can be achieved by a module or layer that interacts with DLT to store and retrieve router-specific updates in a secure and transparent manner. Secure data exchange between routers in IDNs and DLT systems can be achieved with a secure communication protocol (e.g., DIDComm) which ensures that only the desired data can be stored in the DLT and all private data is excluded. Smart contract-based trust verification provides proof of trust through the DLT by verifying the authenticity and integrity of the data exchanged between ASs. Permissioned DLT can also be used to ensure privacy by allowing only authorized entities to access the DLT. To achieve this, access control mechanisms

and encryption techniques can be implemented to protect the data in the DLT.

B. Design of Smart Contracts

Smart contracts on BCN-based SSI are also used to perform verification during the registration process. When a new device is registered for the first time and a new issue request is received for its identity, the smart contract on BCN-based SSI checks whether the records in the export list have already been used on the incoming device so that there is no conflict. If another device has already exported these addresses, the device may not be able to register in the BCN-based SSI. This will ensure in advance that a forwarding problem affecting all ASs will not occur. If the import list on the device is imported into the AS from any device within the AS, this may be reported as a warning to the issuer after the control process.

In some cases, a provisional process may be required after the initial registration of the device, or a device may be moved from one location to another. In the case of migration, the identity of the device is not deleted, but it is sufficient to update the attributes it possesses. In the case of initial registration or migration, it may be desirable to perform pre-identification to update attributes. In this case, a separate smart contract is used. This smart contract waits in the hold state and is triggered and writes the device’s information to the BCN-based SSI when the device becomes accessible on the network. Note that if a device is to be completely removed from the system, its digital ID should also be revoked from the system. In this case, a revocation smart contract can also be implemented.

C. Privacy Policy

Since the issuers are registered in the system and the devices belonging to the issuers are registered in a BCN, the information which device was registered by which issuer is publicly visible. This may be undesirable from a data protection perspective. To protect the privacy of issuers and their registered devices in a BCN, techniques such as encryption of all sensitive data, including device and issuer information, before it is stored on the BCN, using permissioned BCN to allow only authorized parties to access the data, limited visibility such as allowing necessary information to be visible (e.g., the device registration number) while sensitive information is hidden (e.g., the identity of the issuer). In this case, issuers may write the hash values of the device IDs that they issue to the BCN, so that device and service/cloud provider information is not be disclosed. In addition, multi-party computation methods may be used in the information written to the BCN by issuers.

D. SDN Scenario

In this section, we show how the identity plane should be positioned in a Software Defined Networking (SDN)-based architecture. The identity plane is located as a separate layer on top of the control plane, as shown in Fig. 3. The operations related to device identities that affect forwarding are performed in the identity plane. For implementation, identity

Fig. 3: Identity plane for routing management operations.

transactions can be performed through the SDN controller with OpenFlow ID, which is already present in SDN-based devices. The SDN controller registers the OpenFlow ID of each device via an issuer. Then, this registered ID is stored on the BCN-based SSI as the digital identity of that device. The operations required for the identity of the device are then performed using SSI application embedded in the device. The information stored at the identity plane directly affects the configuration and inventory management of devices. The DevOps and infrastructure level concepts shown in Fig. 3 relate to legacy devices (c.f., the SDN forwarding and control planes). Note that identity management processes for legacy devices can be implemented with scripts written at the DevOps level.

III. SSI SOLUTION FOR ROUTING IN INTER-DOMAIN NETWORKS

A. Working Principles

The BCN-based SSI solution for routing in IDNs offers several benefits over traditional routing protocols. It provides a secure and private communication channel by leveraging BCN-based SSI, which ensures that only trusted network equipment is used for routing. It also enables network entities to manage their own identity information and digital credentials. Fig. 2 shows the process of the BCN-based SSI using routing in IDNs. The main idea of the proposed method is to establish trust between routing devices in ASs while keeping the identity and data of the routers private, resulting in only an imperceptible delay in convergence. Integration enables routers in autonomous systems to control routing updates. The interaction also enables secure and transparent execution of routing-related transactions without the need for a central authority. The process consists of the following main phases.

Steps-(1-2) Registration and authentication: To establish communication between AS within the IDNs system, an AS undergoes a registration phase to verify its identity. During this phase, the AS registers its identities, such as IP ranges, with the SSI system using the identity issuer. If the registration process fails, the AS is prohibited from participating in the IDNs routing protocol.

Step-(3) Connection request: Following the successful registration of the new AS, the next phase involves initiating the connection request to establish a routing path between the new destination AS-1 and the source AS-3.

Step-(4) Verify identity and establish connection: In this step, the connection request from AS-1 to AS-3 is verified using the BCN-based SSI. Source AS-3 retrieves digital credentials of destination AS-1 from BCN-based SSI. Credentials can be verified by AS-3 using SSI, which ensures that credentials are valid without revealing additional information about AS-1. The source AS-1 then creates a secure routing path to the destination AS-3 by encrypting the routing information with a shared secret key derived from the digital credentials. A route path is created using these trusted network equipment, such as routers and switches, which are verified against their digital credentials stored on the BCN-based SSI.

Step-(5) Synchronize: In this step, information about the newly established connection is distributed from AS-1 to other ASs to enable synchronization of the router identifications (e.g. export and import list, capabilities, etc.).

B. Issuer, Digital Identity and Attributes

In our proposed method, issuers can be service providers. However, the authority to be an issuer may be granted under the supervision of a global institution such as International Telecommunication Union (ITU), Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) or RIPE. Thus, the authority to be an issuer can be taken under control. Identity control transactions can be performed by institutions that have the authority to control identity, and not necessarily by issuers.

The BCN-based SSI solution for routing in IDNs aims to improve routing security and data protection. The solution uses a distributed ledger to store identity information and digital credentials of network entities, such as ASs and network operators. Each network entity is represented by a unique identity in the BCN that is associated with its digital credentials. As shown in Fig. 2, the identity of a device to be used for an inter-AS connection may include the following information: a ID information paired with the device (Media Access Control (MAC) address may be used for legacy devices), a capability information of the device (supported basic network protocols, data encryption capability, bandwidth capability, etc.), an import and export list containing IP information that is allowed to transmit in the AS.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

A. Test Setup

For validation purposes, an experimental setup is created using the emulation environment GNS3, as shown in Fig. 4. We created two separate ASs in GNS3. We ran a total of four Cisco routers in each AS. One router in each AS is connected to the other as a border router. Border routers use the BGP protocol among themselves. A link-state routing protocol works when ASs are present. Inter-AS BGP routes and link state protocols running on ASs are synchronized with each other. Each AS is configured with a Virtual Machine (VM) connected to that AS and running in a separate VM with

TABLE I
AVERAGE VALUES OF EXPERIMENTAL DID
IMPLEMENTATION FOR CREDENTIAL OPERATIONS

KPI (time, msec)	2/3/4 Border Routers
Average credential presentation	≈ 2
Average credential offer	≈ 35
Average DIDcomm connection creation	≈ 44
Average DIDcomm signing	≈ 5
Average DIDcomm revoke credential	≈ 15

Ansible. Ansible communicates with the BCN-based SSI, with scripts. The BCN-based SSI, on the other hand, works from a separate machine. To measure time, we used Wireshark to monitor various points on the network.

For DIM experiments, we implemented a container-based Hyperledger Indy as a Decentralized Identifier (DID) system on OpenStack, in a VM. During the Hyperledger Indy installation, the von network setup² was performed, on which container-based nodes will run. Hyperledger Indy was used for the DID BCN, and four DID container nodes were created as DID issuers and two border routers in two different ASs to which digital identities were assigned by BCN-based SSI. A REST server is also operated to handle requests to Hyperledger Indy. All communication with BCN-based SSI is done securely using the DIDComm protocol.

B. Results

Average values for various Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to the experimental implementation of DID for credential operations to determine their performance are provided in Table I. KPIs include the average time for credential presentation (time it takes a client to present a credential during the verification process), offer (time it takes a client to offer a credential during the credential exchange process), DID communication (DIDcomm) connection creation (time required by a client to create a DIDcomm connection during the DID exchange process), signing (time required by a client to sign a DIDcomm message during the DID exchange process), and revocation (time required by a client to revoke a credential during the revocation process). The numerical values in the table are given for three different scenarios with 2, 3 and 5 clients. On average, credential presentation takes about 2 milliseconds and credential offer takes about 35 milliseconds for 2/3/4 clients. On average, creating a DIDcomm connection takes about 44 milliseconds and DIDcomm signing takes about 5 milliseconds for 2/3/4 clients. Finally, the average time to revoke a credential with DIDcomm is about 15 milliseconds for all three client scenarios. These results provide insight into the performance of DIM systems with respect to credential operations and suggest that DIM systems can potentially provide fast and secure credential operations in various applications such as identity verification and authentication.

Table II presents the performance metrics of inter-domain and intra-domain networks in terms of the number of border routers and internal routers, respectively. The first column

²VON Network, Available: <https://github.com/bcgov/von-network>, Online: March 2023.

Fig. 4: Experimental setup created using the GNS3 emulation.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE OF INTER-AS CONNECTION AND
INTRA-AS CONVERGENCE TIME WITH DIFFERENT
NUMBER OF ROUTERS INSIDE AS.

Inter AS Connection Time	# of Border Routers	Duration (seconds)
	2	0.3
3	2.25	
4	2.45	
Intra AS Convergence Time	# of Internal Routers	Duration (seconds)
	3	2.505
	4	2.510
5	2.512	

represents the type of network and the second column shows the number of routers in that network. The third column gives the duration of the convergence time in seconds for the corresponding network. These metrics can be used to evaluate and compare the performance of different networks in terms of their convergence time. The duration of inter-AS connection increases with the number of border routers, with a significant jump from 2 to 3 border routers. It increases from 0.3 seconds with 2 border routers to 2.25 seconds with 3 border routers and then increases slightly to 2.45 seconds with 4 border routers. In contrast, the duration of intra-AS convergence time remains relatively stable as the number of internal routers increases, with a small increase from 2.505 seconds with 3 internal routers to 2.510 seconds with 4 internal routers, and then another small increase to 2.512 seconds with 5 internal routers. The duration of inter-AS connection is much shorter than that of intra-AS convergence time, even with a small number of routers. The intra-AS convergence time is longer than the inter-AS connection time, but the difference is smaller for a small number of internal routers (e.g., 2.25 vs. 2.505 seconds for 3 routers). The duration of the inter-AS connection depends strongly on the number of border routers, while the duration of the intra-AS convergence time depends less on the number of internal routers.

Together with Tables I and II insights into the performance of routing in IDNs combined with DID systems can be observed with respect to time. The results for the inter-AS and

intra-AS systems show that as the number of border routers and internal routers increases, more time (on the order of seconds) is needed, while shorter durations are observed for credential operations.

C. Challenges and Possible Solutions

BCN-based SSI for routing in IDNs has the potential to enhance privacy and security in network communications. However, this approach faces several challenges, including:

- **Scalability:** The BCN used for SSI requires a significant amount of computational resources, which can lead to scalability issues in large IDNs. Possible solutions include the use of sharding and off-chain protocols. Moreover, a BCN platform can also be deployed in each Internet exchange point (IXP). Although permissioned BCNs are used in our experiments, permissionless BCNs can also be used to overcome the limits of collusion and overriding consensus. On the other hand, permissioned BCNs may have scalability issues.
- **BCN Platforms:** Hyperledger Indy may be limited in some smart contract customizations. As a solution, solutions such as Cosmos or Zilliqa BCNs can be used to improve performance and gain flexibility in Application Programming Interfaces (APIs).
- **Interoperability:** IDNs consist of multiple domains, and each domain may use different BCN technologies, making it difficult to establish interoperability between them. One solution is to use common standards and protocols for SSI, such as the W3C Verifiable Credentials and DIDs.
- **Governance:** The decentralized nature of BCN makes it challenging to establish governance frameworks for SSI in IDNs. One solution would be to create a decentralized autonomous organization (DAO) that allows stakeholders to participate in decision-making processes.
- **Security and Privacy:** While SSI is intended to enhance user data privacy, the BCN-based identity system can potentially expose sensitive information. One solution is to use ZKPs to authenticate devices without revealing sensitive information (e.g., the issuer name). SSI

in IDNs is also vulnerable to security threats such as 51% attacks and double-spending. Possible solutions are the implementation of consensus mechanisms and multi-factor authentication.

In summary, the challenges facing IDNs with BCN-based SSI require innovative solutions that balance privacy, security, and scalability. By adopting common standards, protocols, BCN platforms, and governance frameworks, it is possible to create a robust and secure BCN-based SSI system that can improve privacy and security in IDNs.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

The use of DIM for inter and intra AS routing in IDNs provides a variety of capabilities that pave the way for control over the use of device-level information in establishing secure routing. In this paper, we have proposed a method for integrating DIM with ASs, enabled by an identity management layer that provides authentication for routing in IDNs. For evaluations, we built an experimental testbed using GNS-3 emulation for routing between AS and Hyperledger Indy as DIM. From the experimental results, it can be concluded that the integration of a blockchain-based credential management of SSI system with the proposed routing in an IDNs-based approach is able to improve the security and efficiency to a significant extent. As future work, we intend to explore and discuss the potential applications of BCN-based SSI in various domains beyond routing, such as identity verification for Internet of Things (IoT), roaming services, subscriber identity management, and secure identity verification for network service provisioning. A broader overview of the challenges and considerations associated with the use of BCN-based SSI in such diverse scenarios may be of interest.

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